
Results of Implementing the National Target Program New Rural Area Construction in 2024 in Duc Tho District, Ha Tinh Province

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ABSTRACT: The article evaluates the results of the implementation of the National Target Program on New Rural Construction in 2024 in Duc Tho district, Ha Tinh province, highlighting the achievements in completing the criteria of new rural areas, advanced new rural areas and model rural areas at both district and commune levels. The study analyzes the results achieved in the fields of economy, infrastructure, culture - society and environment. At the same time, the article also frankly points out the shortcomings, limitations and analyzes the causes, including issues such as the progress of implementing some targets not meeting the plan, ineffective propaganda work in some localities, and the degradation of some residential areas after meeting the standards. Based on the analysis and evaluation, the article proposes a series of solutions to continue implementing the program more effectively in 2025. These solutions focus on strengthening leadership and direction, promoting propaganda, raising people's awareness, developing rural economy, improving infrastructure, developing culture - society, protecting the environment and maintaining invested construction works.

KEYWORDS: new rural areas, Duc Tho, Ha Tinh

1. INTRODUCTION

The New Rural Development Program in Vietnam is implemented to improve the quality of life for people in rural areas, improve infrastructure and develop sustainable economy [1], [2], [3]. The main goal of the program is to build rural communes with good material and spiritual life, encourage community participation in development activities [4]. Since its implementation, many communes have completed the new rural criteria, with significantly improved transport infrastructure, schools and health facilities [5]. The program also helps reduce poverty rates and create jobs for rural workers through effective agricultural production and consumption models. These achievements not only help improve living standards but also create community cohesion, promoting socio-economic development in rural areas of Vietnam [6], [7]. The National Target Program on New Rural Development has made an important contribution to improving the quality of life and promoting economic development in rural areas [8], [9], [10]. In Duc Tho district, Ha Tinh province, 2024 marks an important milestone with outstanding achievements in implementing new rural goals. The district has fully completed 9/9 criteria for a new rural district, and at the same time met 9/9 criteria for an advanced new rural district, affirming the sustainable development of the locality. The dossier for the district to meet the advanced new rural standards in 2024 is currently in the process of assessment and appraisal by the provincial People's Committee and related departments and branches (Committee Duc Tho District People's, 2024). At the commune level, the district has achieved many notable successes with Tan Dan commune completing the advanced new rural criteria, and two communes, Bui La Nhan and Quang Vinh, being recognized as model new rural communes. At the same time, Duc Tho district has also developed 10 more model new rural residential areas, improving the quality of the living environment. The OCOP program in the district also recorded growth when there were three more products meeting 3-star standards, contributing to promoting local economic development. These results reflect the efforts, perseverance and strategic direction of Duc Tho district in implementing the goals of building new rural areas, while opening up new opportunities for the development of rural areas.

This study aims to answer the following questions: What are the results of implementing the national target program on building new rural areas in Duc Tho district? Point out the shortcomings and limitations so that the program can be implemented better? What solutions should the district implement in 2025?

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2. DATABASE AND RESEARCH METHODS

2.1. Database: The article uses data collected from legal documents and policies of the Party and State related to new rural construction. In addition, data on natural conditions and socio-economic conditions of the locality are important data sources for evaluating research results. Statistical information contained in these documents will serve as a basis for analyzing and evaluating the implementation process of new rural programs in the locality.

2.2. Research method:

Field survey method: This method is used to collect data on natural conditions, natural resource potential and socio-economic situation of the locality. During the survey, the research combines the collection of actual data and direct observation to evaluate the implementation of related criteria, especially environmental and food safety criteria in the locality. Combining these two factors helps provide a comprehensive view of the actual situation of the criteria in the commune.

Comparison method: The comparison method is applied to compare specific criteria in the National Target Program on New Rural Development and the achieved criteria of Duc Tho district. This comparison helps to assess the level of achievement of the criteria for the specific conditions of the locality, thereby giving specific comments and recommendations.

3. RESEARCH RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. Socio-economic situation of Duc Tho district

Duc Tho district is located in the north of Ha Tinh province, with an area of 20,349.86 hectares, an average population of 101,300 people in 2024, 16 administrative units at the commune level, including Duc Tho town (district capital) and 15 communes.

Duc Tho is a district with a fairly favorable natural geographical location, a system of canals and rivers convenient for irrigation, economic development and transportation. There is a North-South railway running through with a length of 15km, there are 2 stations, of which Yen Trung station is the main station of Ha Tinh province, with National Highway 8A, Provincial Highway 15A and 5A passing through. Based on natural conditions, geographical location, belts and soil, Duc Tho is divided into 3 distinct regions: Upper region, inside dike region and outside dike region. Each region has its own strengths in developing agriculture, livestock, trade, services and tourism.

Duc Tho countryside changes its appearance day by day, month by month, by the end of 2019, 27/27 communes achieved new rural status, Tung Anh commune achieved model new rural status, Duc Yen achieved advanced new rural status, houses are built close together. People's lives are constantly improving, security, social order and safety are always stable. By 2019, the poverty rate in Duc Tho district was only 3.99%, average income per capita reached 38 million VND. Economic structure: Agriculture 20.1%; Industry - Construction 37.8%; Trade - Services 42.1%; In June 2020, Duc Tho was recognized by the Prime Minister as a new rural district.

Duc Tho tourism potential is rich and diverse, with many beautiful landscapes, many long-standing historical and cultural relics, playing a major role in attracting tourists to visit and tour. Currently, the district has 94 relics, of which 14 are ranked, typically Nguyen Bieu cultural relics, Phan Dinh Phung tomb, historical relics, architectural and artistic relics including communal houses, pagodas, temples, shrines, typically Am pagoda, Phuong Thanh. Typical revolutionary relics such as the tomb and memorial house of the late General Secretary Tran Phu, the relic groups combined with the existing natural ecological environment of the district will form a spiritual - ecological tour from Duc Tho town to Am pagoda, Phuong Thanh - Phan Dinh Phung tomb, memorial area and Tran Phu tomb back to Tam Soa wharf, then down the La river. This spiritual - ecological tour is currently being surveyed and planned to establish a feasible project. The potential of natural tourism combined with cultural tourism will create a significant resource for the socio-economic development of the district in the coming years, in joint ventures and partnerships with major tourist centers of the region and the province.

3.2. Results of the implementation of the National Target Program on New Rural Development in Duc Tho District in 2024

3.2.1. Results of implementation by fields

3.2.1.1. Economy and production organization:

- Agricultural production: 2024 is a year of comprehensive harvest in terms of both productivity and area, with a total production area of 15,481/14,962 hectares, reaching 103.5% of the annual plan. Total grain output is 72,951 tons, reaching 109.2% of the plan. The value of harvested products/ha in cultivation reaches 125 million VND/ha. Production linked with enterprises is promoted, signing an organic production cooperation agreement with Que Lam Group, linking cassava production with Nghe An Agriculture, Forestry and Fishery Company. Guiding communes and towns to accumulate land.
- Industry - Small industry - Construction: Estimated production value reached 2,845 billion VND, equivalent to 101.4% of the plan. Directing the development of production in industrial clusters in the area. In Thai Yen industrial cluster, there are 90 projects and enterprises renting land, with an area of 7.24 ha, the occupancy rate is 72%. In Duc Tho district industrial cluster, the provincial People's Committee has approved the adjustment of detailed planning with a total area of 68.28 ha. Truong Son Industrial Cluster continues to maintain and develop the production and trading of wooden furniture.

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- Trade - Services: Total circulation of goods and service revenue is estimated at 3,184 billion VND, reaching 102.5% of the plan. Organizing market inspection and control of product quality measurement, food hygiene and safety, price listing and conformity marking, origin of goods, etc. at business locations and kiosks.
- Newly established 40/20 enterprises reaching 200%, 3 cooperatives, 74/66 models reaching 112.1% (3/3 large models reaching 100%, 22/18 medium models reaching 122.2%; 49/45 small models reaching 108.9%) of which 27 models are in the handicraft sector.
- One Commune One Product (OCOP) Program: Organizing the assessment and classification of Ocop-standard products, adding 3 more products meeting 3-star Ocop standards and 2 products being re-assessed, bringing the total number of Ocop-standard products in the district to 34. Organizing 3 training courses on One Commune One Product Program, Digital Transformation in Production and Business for Farmers, Youth Union, and Women to start businesses associated with Ocop products.

3.2.1.2. Socio-economic infrastructure development - Received 1,283.2/1,875.2 tons of cement, reaching 68.4% of the plan. Renovated 20.45 km of rural roads (from the cement mechanism, 8.435/12.9 km reached 65.4%), 5.5 km of intra-field roads (0.785/2.1 km from the cement mechanism reached 37.4%), 5.8 km of drainage ditches in residential areas, 11.125 km of hard canals (3.575/3.5 km from the cement mechanism reached 102.1%, 7.55 km from project sources); laid 35.9 km of carbon asphalt and hot asphalt (of which 19.44 from the support mechanism of the province and district, reaching 101.7%). Built 1 new communal cultural house, 1 village cultural house; 4 entertainment areas. Upgrading and constructing 15 village sports areas. Building 3 grocery stores, 5 markets with upgraded items; 89 houses for poor households and policy households. Expanding and clearing land to build 17.7km of rural roads; filling and paving 26km of roadsides. Upgrading and renovating 44.2km of lighting lines, relocating 61 electric poles after expanding roads in communes. - Schools: Building 13 new classrooms, 29 subject classrooms, 28 administrative rooms, 7 multi-purpose houses, 15 toilets. Upgrading and upgrading 41 classrooms, 20 subject classrooms, 41 administrative rooms, 3 toilets, 2 multi-purpose houses

3.2.1.3. Building model new rural residential areas, smart villages

There are 10 more standard model residential areas, bringing the total number of villages in the district to 130/142 that meet the model new rural standards, a rate of 91.5%.

Some results: Building and planting 57km of new flower beds and green fences; planting 4,895 shade trees. Renovating and refurbishing 1,562 household gardens, 424 mixed gardens; 7,384 households arranged their houses neatly and tidily. Renovating and upgrading 174 auxiliary works; demolishing 325 unsatisfactory sanitary works to build septic tanks, 117 unused sanitary works; renovating, renovating and upgrading 290 livestock works; Installing 730 models of domestic wastewater treatment, 1,970 billboards and propaganda signs. Organize 6 training, propaganda and guidance classes on building model new rural residential areas; classifying and treating waste; 5 families in Hoa Lac, Truong Son, Duc Dong and An Dung communes.

- Smart residential areas: In 2024, build 5 more smart residential areas, of which 2/5 villages (Vinh Phuc - Quang Vinh; Ha Tu - Bui La Nhan) have been assessed by the Department of Information and Communications, bringing the total number of residential areas in the district to 5 meeting smart residential area standards. Specific implementation results in the villages are as follows:
 - + Ha Tu village: Install 4 security cameras; smart radio. Pour and widen 100m of sidewalk; renew 60m of rural roads. Establish an online information exchange channel.
 - + Dong Thai village: Purchase portable speakers; computers, printers at the cultural house; install 4 sets of security cameras, 5 sets of decorative welcome gates across the road; Purchase sports equipment at the playground. Mobilize people to donate 372m² of land, 600m of fence to expand 0.36km of traffic roads, build 0.6km of roads around the ecological lake; build 0.15km of drainage ditches. Build a flower road.
 - + Chau Noi village: Purchase portable speakers; computers, printers at the cultural house. Build 56m of traffic roads, 0.86km of lighting lines on the village axis. Clear and expand 0.22km of rural traffic roads. Build flower roads, village welcome gates.
 - + Trung Khanh village: Mobilize people to donate 450m² of land to expand traffic roads. Build 0.45km of traffic roads and drainage ditches. Install 7 security cameras, smart speaker system, 0.45km of residential lighting lines, 16 solar-powered lamp posts. Build 01 clean and beautiful green road. Purchase and supplement equipment at the cultural house (camera, TV, solar lights). Create QR code for the village cultural house, historical site of Le family church.
 - + Vinh Phuc Village: Install 5 security cameras; purchase projectors, computers, televisions at the village cultural house, smart village radio, smart lighting system, 56 propaganda boards. Establish zalo group as an online information exchange channel.

3.2.1.4 Culture, society, environment

Organize propaganda work well to serve holidays and socio-political tasks in the district. Organize 08 district-level sports competitions, participate in 7 provincial-level sports competitions. Build and recognize 30,488 cultural families; 142/142 villages achieve the title of cultural village. Synchronously and effectively deploy solutions in teaching and educational activities to ensure the completion of the 2023-2024 school year plan in accordance with regulations, with comprehensive and solid results. School

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facilities have been significantly improved, during the school year, 10 schools were recognized as meeting national standards; bringing the total number of schools in the district to 51/58 meeting national standards, of which 26/58 schools met level 2 standards, accounting for 44.8%. The rate of people participating in health insurance reached 97.03%; The rate of children under 5 years old with height/age malnutrition was 10.5%. The rate of trained workers reached 78.6%; 1,700 workers were employed. The rate of poor households was 2.34%, the rate of near-poor households was 2.64%.

Strengthening propaganda on waste classification and treatment at households. Installing 730 models of domestic wastewater treatment, 155 pesticide collection tanks in the fields. Continuing to transport waste to the Ky Anh waste treatment plant for treatment, an average of 30 - 33 tons/day.

3.2.2. Implementation results for the indicators of advanced new rural districts

3.2.2.1. Indicator of 100% of communes meeting new rural standards, at least 50% of communes meeting advanced new rural standards, 10% of communes meeting model new rural standards:

Up to now, the whole district has 15/15 communes meeting new rural standards, 8/15 communes meeting advanced new rural standards reaching 53.3%, 4/15 communes (Tung Anh, Lam Trung Thuy, Thanh Binh Thinh, Yen Ho) meeting model new rural standards reaching 26.7%. Advanced new rural communes (Tan Dan); model new rural communes (Bui La Nhan, Quang Vinh) are being assessed by departments and branches to meet advanced new rural standards, model communes in 2024.

3.2.2.2. Regarding the criteria for building a district that meets the advanced new rural standards

- Meet 9/9 criteria (No. 1 Planning; No. 2 Transportation; No. 3 Irrigation and disaster prevention; No. 4 Electricity; No. 5 Health - Culture - Education; No. 6 Economy; No. 7 Environment; No. 8 Quality of living environment; No. 9 Security, order - Public administration). Complete the dossier of the district meeting the advanced new rural standards and submit it to the Provincial People's Committee, departments and branches for inspection and appraisal to meet the standards of the district meeting the advanced new rural standards in 2024. Up to now, the departments and branches are coming to evaluate and appraise.

- Implementation results in 2024:

- + Departments and branches, specialized in the field in charge, based on the sets of criteria and instructions of the departments and branches, complete the dossier of indicators and criteria for new rural districts and advanced new rural districts.
- + Planning: Adjusting the district planning project to 2035, with a vision to 2050 approved by the Provincial People's Committee in Decision 2223 dated September 18, 2024, announcing the adjustment of the district planning.
- + Traffic: Constructing and upgrading routes DH 46, DH 56, DH 53, DH 48; installing additional signs and speed bumps on district routes to ensure regulations. Completing documents to start construction of the central bus station at the new planning location.
- + Health - Culture - Education: Recognizing the town as meeting the standards of a civilized urban area. Renovating and embellishing Tien Lu pagoda and Tran Duc church. Upgrading and embellishing the district square. Construction of a 4-storey building for the district medical center; parking lots for Duc Tho and Minh Khai high schools. The vocational education and continuing education center arrange a library, purchases equipment, and is recognized by the Department of Education and Training as having achieved educational quality accreditation in Decision No. 1155/QD-SGDĐT dated October 1, 2024. Complete the procedures to start construction of the multi-purpose building of Minh Khai High School.
- + Economy: Build a tourism section on the district's electronic information portal; check-in point at Tam Soa wharf. Work with localities and households in need of building "Homestay" tourist accommodation facilities. Issue planting area codes for 178.3 hectares of rice production, 5 hectares of corn and 35 hectares of peanut production. Renovate and upgrade Hom market.
- + Environment: Buy 01 specialized vehicle for collecting and transporting garbage; Thanh Binh Thinh, Yen Ho, Quang Vinh, Bui La Nhan, and An Dung communes implement the collection and transportation of household waste to be treated at Ky Tan waste treatment plant periodically once a week; Transporting waste to Ky Anh, processing an average of 30-33 tons/day. Installing an automatic monitoring system at Thai Yen industrial park. + Quality of living environment: Completing the surface water treatment model of Bau Quan lake; building a smart commune model in Tung Anh commune. Deploying the installation of a clean water supply pipeline system for Tan Dan commune.

3.3. Existence, limitations, causes

3.3.1. Existence, limitations

- Propaganda, leadership, and direction of the implementation of socio-economic development tasks and new rural construction in some localities and units have not been focused on.
- The progress of implementing some targets and criteria has not met the set plan, such as building a smart new rural commune model, upgrading squares and installing outdoor sports equipment, building bus stations at new planning locations, starting construction of multi-purpose buildings for Nguyen Thi Minh Khai High School, etc.
- The movement to build rural roads - intra-field traffic in some localities has not received attention, and implementation has not met the plan (reaching 61.5% of the plan).

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- Newly established models are mainly small-scale models, lacking linkages in production (49/74 models, accounting for 66.2%). The development of small-scale industrial - trade and service models is uneven, mainly concentrated in some potential communes. Owners of production establishments, enterprises, cooperatives... are not really interested in participating in the One Commune One Product (OCOP) Program; some products have expired but have not participated in re-evaluation and recognition. Products that meet standards have not focused on promotion, introduction, and trade promotion, and participation in fairs is limited... - Some residential areas have been assessed and recognized as meeting standards and have enjoyed policies, but up to now they have seriously degraded, lacking the attention of people and village officials, especially in the criteria: Arrangement of houses, auxiliary works; rearrangement of household gardens, livestock facilities; environmental landscape... Communes are focusing on villages registered to meet the standards of new-style rural residential areas in the year; lack of attention to directing the maintenance and upgrading of criteria in recognized villages has led to many villages degrading. After meeting the standards, some model gardens are not sustainably maintained, the efficiency from the gardens is not high, and there is a lack of uniformity.

3.3.2. Reasons

Objectively:

- The regulations of the set of criteria for communes meeting the standards of new rural areas, advanced new rural areas, and model rural areas in the period of 2022-2025 have some higher indicators and criteria than the previous period.
- Many localities have a low starting point and limited revenue. The source of funding support from the central budget and provincial budget for agricultural and rural investment, especially for the New Rural Development Program, is still limited and decreasing. Access to credit capital for production development is still difficult.

Subjectively:

- The awareness of some experts in departments and branches assigned to be in charge of criteria, members of the working group assigned to be in charge of communes is not close, lacking enthusiasm. Some departments, agencies and sectors lack attention and inspection in the implementation of leadership and direction in communes and towns. Coordination between levels, sectors and localities is still limited; not closely following the grassroots, not proactive in advising; there is still a phenomenon of pushing and avoiding tasks and responsibilities.
- The leadership and direction of the implementation of the New Rural Development Program in some localities and units is not focused. The participation of the people is still limited, in some localities, the New Rural Development Program is mainly implemented by commune-level officials and civil servants, people still wait and rely on it.
- District budget revenue is still limited; difficulties in mobilizing resources to complete the criteria in new rural development.
- Awareness of officials of departments and sectors at district and grassroots levels about the OCOP Program is still limited; Communes and towns have not really paid attention to and have not determined the importance, role and significance of the OCOP program for rural economic development, so in the past, the coordination, direction and support of communes and towns; and the association levels have not been drastic and in-depth. - The survey and assessment of each content and criteria for building model residential areas in some villages have not been thorough; the development of plans, estimates, and frameworks for implementation guidance are still formal, the data is not scientific, so in the implementation process, it is necessary to both consolidate and review, and adjust and supplement, leading to confusion in the implementation organization and failure to achieve the set plan.

3.4. Objectives, tasks and solutions in 2025

3.4.1. Objectives

- Maintain and improve 9 criteria for advanced new rural districts.
- Build 02 more communes to meet advanced new rural standards; 01 commune to meet model new rural standards; the remaining communes sustainably maintain the criteria. Build 03 more villages to meet model new rural residential areas; 3 products to meet OCOP standards.
- Build: 25 km of roads (including: 20 km of rural roads; 5 km of intra-field roads); upgrade and renew 10 km of hard canals (including 3.5 km from cement support). Build school facilities to recognize 01 new national standard school; 02 schools re-tested to meet standard 1; 02 schools re-tested to meet standard 2.
- Establish 20 Enterprises; The rate of effective cooperatives reached 70%; 70 economic models were built.
- Average income per capita reached 65 million VND. Value of harvested products/ha in cultivation: 130 million VND/ha.
- The rate of trained workers reached 80%; the annual poverty rate decreased by 0.4-0.5%; the rate of people participating in health insurance was 96%; the rate of children with malnutrition in height/age was reduced by 10%; 30,490 cultural families and 155 cultural villages were recognized.
- The rate of households using clean water reached 100% (of which the rate of clean water was 85%).
- Completed 100% of military recruitment targets; 100% of units met the standards of comprehensively strong bases; 100% of communes and towns had stable security and politics.

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3.4.2. Solution groups

3.4.2.1. Leadership, direction and propaganda work:

- Continue to closely follow the goals and guiding viewpoints of Resolution No. 03-NQ/HU dated September 28, 2021; further promote propaganda work, raise awareness for the entire political system and people to be determined to implement the targets according to the set roadmap. Improve the quality of radio and television activities in the area.
- Maintain weekly meetings in communes and towns; grasp the progress, difficulties and obstacles, propose solutions for implementation; working groups guide and direct communes to build advanced new rural communes and model communes to regularly follow up, guide and urge communes to implement. Launch a peak month for building advanced new rural districts.
- Specialized departments and branches shall, based on the guidance on implementing the criteria for the 2022-2025 period of provincial departments and branches, direct and guide localities to review, develop a planning framework and implement to consolidate and improve the achieved criteria, and complete the unmet criteria.
- Officials at all levels and branches must always accompany communes and villages in the process of deployment and implementation; assign specific tasks to each organization and union according to each content, criterion, plan roadmap, and specific solutions to direct and guide localities in implementing the criteria; regularly inspect and support establishments and people to promptly resolve problems and difficulties in the implementation process. Regularly organize inspections and monitor the results of the implementation of the New Rural Development Program in localities.
- Continue to promote the role of the Fatherland Front and socio-political organizations in propaganda and mobilization of union members and members to actively participate in the New Rural Development Program.

3.4.2.2. *Regarding resource mobilization and policy mechanisms:* Review and arrange projects in order of priority and the ability to balance resources to organize the implementation of contents and criteria according to the plan. Synchronously and effectively implement central and provincial policies; call for and integrate projects to complete works. Maximize the mobilization of resources from enterprises, people and other support capital sources to integrate with State budget investment capital to build infrastructure. Diversify investment forms such as the State and people working together, combined public investment forms, socialized capital, capital from children far from home, promote the spirit of self-reliance and self-reliance of the people in building New Rural Development.

3.4.2.3. *Building criteria for advanced new rural districts:* Specialized departments and branches in their respective fields, based on the assessment and verification reports of departments and branches, focus on completing the contents, targets and criteria to submit to the Government for consideration and recognition of districts that have met advanced new rural standards.

3.4.2.4. Solutions for commune groups:

- For communes that have met the standards: Based on Decisions 36, 38, 15 of the province on promulgating the set of criteria for new rural communes, advanced new rural areas and model new rural areas for the period 2022 - 2025, review and evaluate the results; build a planning framework to complete, sustainably maintain and improve the level of meeting the criteria. Develop production, garden economy; form and build products that meet OCOP standards; create a green, clean and beautiful landscape environment... Build Lam Trung Thuy commune to meet the standards of a smart new rural commune.
- For the group of communes striving to achieve advanced and model new rural standards by 2025: Based on the sets of criteria for the period 2022 - 2025, the guiding documents of the Departments and branches, review and evaluate the results of the implementation of the criteria to build a planning framework, determine the time schedule and capital sources for implementation; assign specific tasks to each member of the Steering Committee to strive to achieve advanced and model new rural standards by 2025.

3.4.2.5. Main solutions for some groups of criteria

- Building socio-economic infrastructure: Strengthen the leadership and direction of the district Party Committee and authorities for the investment and construction of project works in the area. Effectively implement the Project Programs, encourage investment promotion to build essential infrastructure to serve production and people's lives. At the same time, focus on site clearance for project works; Direct and urge contractors to urgently mobilize all resources, speed up the construction progress of projects; promote the timely disbursement of public investment capital in 2025. Effectively implement the grassroots democracy regulations, create all favorable conditions for people and communities to truly take ownership in building the New Rural Area.
- Group of criteria: Economy and production organization:
 - + Promote agricultural development in the direction of focusing on developing high-tech and organic agriculture. Effectively issue land use right certificates after land accumulation; overcome small-scale and fragmented production, gradually form specialized agricultural commodity production areas. Build concentrated production areas in the direction of intensive farming to increase productivity, quality, product value, with planting area codes and traceability; encourage and attract enterprises and organizations

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- to invest in agricultural production; develop traditional products, products with potential advantages, associated with brand building according to the One Commune One Product (OCOP) Program.
- + Continue to resolutely direct the implementation of the Project on industrial development, small-scale industry and craft villages in the district. Review and survey the land rental needs of investors, locations with advantages in planning clusters, small-scale industry, trade and service points, in order to diversify industries and develop production and business in localities.
 - Cultural-social-environmental criteria group:
 - + Implement well the work of sustainable poverty reduction according to the poverty standard for the period 2022-2030; implement social policies well and promptly. Focus on directing vocational training for rural workers, striving for the rate of trained workers to reach 80%.
 - + Continue to consolidate the system of cultural and sports facilities, entertainment facilities in the communes to improve the effectiveness of serving the community; avoid degradation, damage, and waste. Improve the efficiency of cultural and sports institutions; guide the organization of healthy cultural, sports, and entertainment activities, creating conditions to attract people to participate.
 - + Improve the quality of the movement "All people unite to build a cultural life"; cultural titles are associated with building model residential areas; promote the effectiveness of radio broadcasting activities in the area. Promote good cultural values; continue to pay attention to preserving traditional cultural values; invest in the budget and mobilize maximum social resources to preserve heritage values, restore and embellish relics in the area.
 - + Complete information technology infrastructure, databases to serve the digital transformation process; maintain a good telecommunications system (commune and village radio); increase access to online public services at public places, free wifi.
 - + Synchronously implement solutions to maintain and improve the quality of teaching and learning. Strengthen socialization, mobilize resources to invest in facilities and teaching equipment.
 - + Strengthen disease prevention and control. Synchronously implement solutions to improve the quality of medical examination and treatment services, linking and cooperating between levels, inside and outside the province, central hospitals, medical universities.
 - + Continue to mobilize people to ensure the treatment and classification of waste at households to minimize the amount of waste sent for treatment; install a model for domestic wastewater treatment; demolish 2-compartment toilets and build septic tanks. Have support and incentive policies for the collection, transportation and treatment of solid waste.
 - Political system, National Defense - Security: Maintain strict combat readiness, strengthen inspection and practice of plans and strategies to ensure absolute safety for important political and cultural events of the country and locality. Proactively grasp and forecast the situation related to security and order; promote the combined strength of the entire political system and the entire people to participate in the prevention, fight and fight against crimes and social evils;
 - Model residential areas, model gardens:
 - + Focus on propaganda work to build model new rural residential areas, model gardens, propagate good models and good practices; innovate and diversify propaganda forms so that people better understand the role and practical benefits of building model new rural residential areas and model gardens; mobilize maximum participation and contribution of people's intelligence, efforts and resources. + Based on the Model Residential Area Criteria for the period 2022-2025, organize a review and assessment of the current situation; develop a specific and realistic plan, estimate, schedule and implementation roadmap to sustainably maintain the achieved residential areas and complete the remaining residential areas. Promote the development of household garden economy, eliminate mixed gardens and mixed plants, and plant valuable trees.
 - + Create a movement of competition between households, inter-family groups, and villages, and periodically organize competitions to create a widespread and increasingly in-depth competition movement. With the achieved results and valuable lessons learned during the implementation process, people have promoted their role as subjects, proactively and creatively.

4. CONCLUSION

In 2024, Duc Tho district has achieved positive results in implementing the National Target Program on New Rural Construction. The district has completed 9/9 criteria for new rural districts and 9/9 criteria for advanced new rural districts. Many communes have met advanced and model new rural standards. However, besides the successes, there are still some shortcomings and limitations such as the progress of implementing some targets and criteria has not met the plan; propaganda work in some localities has not been drastic; some residential areas have degraded after meeting the standards... To continue to improve the effectiveness of the program in 2025, Duc Tho district needs to focus on the following solutions: Strengthening leadership and direction, promoting propaganda, raising people's awareness of the National Target Program on New Rural Construction. Promoting rural economic development, focusing on production linkages, increasing product value. Continuing to invest in completing infrastructure, especially rural and intra-field transport. Paying attention to cultural and social development, improving people's quality of life. Protecting the environment, responding to climate change. Carry out well the maintenance and repair of invested and constructed

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works to avoid deterioration. The good implementation of the above solutions will contribute significantly to the completion of the set goals, making Duc Tho district increasingly developed.

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